

INTERFACIAL TENSION OF ALIPHATIC ESTERS WITH SURFACE ACTIVE AGENTS. PART II

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The interfacial tension measurements of some aliphatic esters have been carried out against aqueous soap solutions. A number of esters, e.g. propyl, butyl and amyl acetates etc. show an exceptional behaviour in a sense that the tension increases to a sharp maximum initially with increasing soap concentration in dilute solutions, followed by a great lowering and thereafter reaching a limiting value.

In Part I of this series (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 209) the authors reported the unusual behaviour of hexyl and *sec.*-octyl alcohols as regards the increase of interfacial tension over a certain low range of soap concentration. This behaviour is particularly marked with a class of aliphatic esters, viz, ethyl, *isopropyl*, *n*-butyl, *isobutyl*, *isoamyl* acetates, ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl *isovalerate*; while methyl acetate and diethyl malonate do not exhibit such a behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL

The interfacial tension measurements were carried out by the method described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) using sodium and potassium oleate, sodium and potassium stearate, sodium chloride and acetate, and saponin. In case of methyl and ethyl acetates, which are partly miscible with water, if the syringe is filled with ester, the liquid forms a continuous stream in the water phase, instead of drops. Since the proportionate solubility of water in the esters is considerably less than that of esters in water, when water is filled in the syringe, water forms drops at the tip in the ester phase. In this way the interfacial tension of esters against water was determined. The substances were either of standard quality or prepared by the usual method and subsequently purified before use. The results are expressed in Tables I—III and Figs. 1 and 2.

The interfacial tension against water in the ester series is found to be in the following order: methyl < ethyl < *isopropyl* > *n*-butyl > *isobutyl* > *isoamyl*. It appears to be increasing first and then decreasing with the length of the aliphatic chain.

It is also obvious that the extent of the lowering of surface tension by the soap solution depends on its magnitude against water, but *isopropyl* acetate is an exception, where the relative lowering is much less. In case of all esters, except methyl acetate and diethyl malonate, the interfacial tension increases with increasing soap concentration up to 2×10^{-3} M and then diminishes with further increase in the soap concentration, till the limiting value is reached (Table I, Figs. 1 and 2). With saponin, however, it appears to decrease with increasing saponin concentration over the entire range, till the limiting value is reached (Table II). The interfacial tension measurements with *isoamyl* acetate using sodium chloride and sodium acetate, indicate that the tension initially increases with increase in electrolyte concentration and then diminishes with further increase in

electrolyte concentration (Fig. 2). The measurements with *n*-butyl acetate using potassium oleate-neutral, acidic and alkaline-, sodium and potassium stearate show the analogous behaviour (Table III). In general, the interfacial tension depression, follow-

TABLE I
Interfacial tension (dynes/cm.).

Na-oleate ($M \times 10^{-3}$).	Methyl acetate.	Ethyl acetate.	isoPropyl acetate.	<i>n</i> -Butyl acetate.	isoButyl acetate.	isoAmyl acetate.	Ethyl ac- etoacetate.	Ethyl iso- valerate.	Diethyl malonate.
0.000	3.099	6.640	13.93	13.88	13.22	12.11	2.701	18.14	13.03
0.246	2.845	7.119	14.02	18.01	13.89	12.82	3.038	19.32	9.333
0.492	2.735	7.230	14.21	18.35	14.40	13.32	2.789	21.31	8.654
0.984	—	—	14.56	18.57	—	11.41	2.649	22.83	7.354
1.476	—	—	15.24	19.31	12.95	10.17	—	—	—
1.968	2.494	7.389	14.42	18.92	—	9.353	2.562	18.65	6.771
2.460	—	—	14.03	17.09	—	8.847	2.345	14.90	6.506
2.950	—	—	13.72	15.68	9.24	8.023	—	14.06	—
3.936	2.275	7.168	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.920	2.177	6.060	13.41	9.71	7.34	7.415	2.214	12.43	6.243
6.560	—	5.421	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
9.800	—	—	13.32	6.715	—	5.371	2.045	8.134	5.449
14.79	—	—	13.32	6.477	5.94	—	—	6.691	—
19.68	—	—	13.12	6.183	—	5.18	1.635	6.092	—
29.52	—	—	13.03	5.247	5.36	4.537	—	—	—
32.80	—	—	—	—	4.74	4.319	1.296	5.283	4.455
49.20	—	—	12.93	4.863	4.22	4.110	—	—	4.11
98.40	—	—	12.75	4.553	3.08	3.682	—	—	—

TABLE II
Interfacial tension (dynes/cm.).

Saponin.	isoPropyl acetate.	isoButyl acetate.	<i>n</i> -Butyl acetate.	isoAmyl acetate.
0.000 %	13.93	13.22	13.88	12.11
0.0075	8.502	11.47	9.065	9.819
0.015	7.595	9.883	7.608	7.832
0.045	6.577	6.419	5.845	5.882
0.060	5.991	5.636	5.667	5.563
0.090	5.680	5.130	4.778	5.371
0.150	5.069	4.939	4.074	4.528
0.300	4.757	4.617	3.777	4.112
0.450	3.464	4.206	3.592	4.015
0.900	3.149	3.805	3.322	3.792

ing the maximum tension, increases much more rapidly than soap concentration for dilute solutions, thereafter becomes less and ultimately any more increase in soap concentration has practically no effect on it.

TABLE III

Interfacial tension (dynes/cm.).

<i>n</i> -Butyl acetate. ($M \times 10^{-3}$.)	K-oleate.	K-oleate (20% free acid).	K-oleate (20% free alkali).	Na-stearate.	K-stearate.
0.000	13.88	13.88	13.88	13.88	13.88
0.233	14.00	15.25	15.70	15.80	14.88
0.4666	14.46	15.60	16.90	15.95	17.80
0.932	15.86	16.25	17.90	16.75	16.76
1.864	17.53	16.81	19.70	18.65	15.96
2.336	16.46	16.45	19.00	19.45	14.88
2.796	15.95	16.00	18.25	18.20	14.60
4.660	15.57	14.25	15.40	15.55	14.25
9.320	9.63	10.55	9.96	—	12.82

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

Initial increase in interfacial tension of alcohols and esters over the low increasing range of soap concentrations and then its usual decrease, is explained on the basis of these liquids having a ring structure as postulated by Smith and McReynolds (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1963) and further that the reversal of electrical double

layer at the interface of aqueous medium and such a liquid takes place with the variation in soap concentration. From the data of esterification, saponification and dissociation constants, they have postulated that acids with a chain involving four or more carbon atoms have a ring structure. Further, they have stated that irregularities in optical rotatory power, noted by Pickard and Kenyon for homologous alcohol series (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 45) could be satisfactorily interpreted in the light of a ring formed through hydrogen bond and also that the ring structure through hydrogen bond may explain other anomalies, particularly the peculiar effect which the ethyl group often exerts. The effect of the nature of carbon chain on the rate of acid catalysed and base catalysed prototropy of phenylalkyl ketones (Evans and Gordon, *ibid.*, 1938, 1434) may be explained by the formation of such a ring containing four carbons as easily as by the three carbon ring. In this connection, Huggins (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1936, 407) has pointed out that in general, hydrogen bonds are more stable when the distances through which the bond operates are small. This type of ring must by its very nature be quite unstable. Liquids, referred to above, should have this type of unstable ring structure through the hydrogen bond. There is formed at the interface of such a liquid and aqueous phase an electrical double layer, as suggested by Helmholtz, Gouy and others (McBain, "Colloid Science", 1950) and correspondingly, there exists a double layer potential.

Much work has been done by Beutner, Loeb and Baur (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, 19, 509; 1926, 32, 547; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 104, 472; *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1923, 42, 656) on potential differences existing between organic liquids and aqueous salt solutions. The double layer potential, which is due to the preferential adsorption of one or the other ion on the liquid interface, has been found to change, when the composition of the aqueous phase is changed.

The relation between double layer potential and interfacial tension between mercury and aqueous solution was first studied by Lippmann and others (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1875, 5, 494; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 154, 454; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 439). With increasing applied potential, the charge on mercury decreases and is then neutralised, the interfacial tension increases while this happens, reaching a maximum, when the charge is annulled. Further increase of potential develops opposite charge on the mercury, and the tension again begins to fall.

In the present work, such a double layer potential between the organic liquid and aqueous phase is presumed to be decreased by increasing ionic atmosphere in very dilute solutions with increase in soap concentration. With the consequent lowering of charge density at the interface, it is accompanied by an increase of surface tension. When the potential of the double layer is completely annulled by the increasing ionic atmosphere, the interfacial tension will be maximum. With increasing soap concentration, however, a double layer of opposite sign to the original will be formed, and the sign of potential is now reversed; with increase in charge density of this layer, now again the interfacial tension goes on decreasing. The development of the reversal of electrical double layer in case of esters and alcohols, referred to, should be ascribed to the unstable ring structure through the hydrogen bond. In case of other liquids, viz, butyl and

amyl alcohols, diethyl malonate and methyl acetate, there should not be H-bonding possibility, and so the reversal of double layer would not take place. Therefore, there is observed a gradual decrease of interfacial tension with increasing soap concentration over the entire range.

The work on interfacial tension variations at the interface between organic liquids, referred to, and mixed aqueous salt solutions viz., KCl-HgCl_2 , $\text{KNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ etc. indicating complex formations between these salts, provides confirmation for this type of explanation. These results will be discussed in later papers.

In the case of *iso*amyl acetate (Fig. 2) such a behaviour is also observed with a very dilute solution of sodium acetate and sodium chloride, as in the case of colloidal electrolyte, sodium oleate. In a very dilute aqueous solution, the soap behaves like an ordinary electrolyte and is considerably ionised into an alkali metal cation and a fatty acid ion. At an appreciable concentration, however, the anions aggregate together to form ionic micelles (McBain).

With the saponin solution (Table II), however, only the decrease in the interfacial tension is observed with its increasing concentration over the entire range, as it would not provide ionic atmosphere like an electrolyte.

The peak in interfacial tension is maximum with *n*-butyl acetate, ethyl *isovalerate* and *sec*.-octyl alcohol, viz., 5.5, 4.69 and 6.83 dynes/cm. respectively and minimum with hexyl alcohol, ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl acetate, viz., 0.87, 0.33 and 0.74 dynes/cm. respectively. It may be possible that the peak might be related to the degree of stability of the ring character through H-bond in these cases. Further work along these lines is in progress.

The authors are indebted to Dr. B. K. Vaidya, Assistant Director, Ahmedabad Textile Industrial Research Association for his suggestions and interest and also they express their gratitude to the college authority for the grant to meet the expenses incurred in the work.

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Received August 14, 1952.

INTERFACIAL TENSION OF LIQUIDS HAVING H-BOND RING STRUCTURE AND COMPLEX FORMATION. PART I. $\text{HgCl}_2\text{-KCl-H}_2\text{O}$ SYSTEM

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Measurements of interfacial tension between *n*-butyl acetate and solutions containing KCl and HgCl_2 in varying proportions indicate the formation of seven complexes in solution between KCl and HgCl_2 , viz. (1) $4\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (2) $3\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (3) $2\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (4) $3\text{KCl} \cdot 2\text{HgCl}_2$, (5) $\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, (6) $2\text{KCl} \cdot 3\text{HgCl}_2$ and (7) $\text{KCl} \cdot 2\text{HgCl}_2$.

The formation of three complexes between HgCl_2 and KCl in solution, namely, $\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, $2\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, and $3\text{KCl} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ has been shown by measurements of solubility, conductivity and surface tension (Tichomiroff, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 39, 731; Foote, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 38, 236; Arcay and Marcot, *Compt. rend.*,